

Designing a three layer supply chain considering different transportation channels and delivery time dependent demand

Hanie Hasanzadeh and [Mehdi Seifbarghy](#)

Department of Industrial Engineering, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

The present study is devoted to designing a three-layer supply chain including a number of plants, distribution centers, and customers, demanding for multiple products. A model is proposed in which the objective function is to maximize the profit, calculated by subtracting costs from incomes. The customers' demand is assumed to be dependent on the delivery time. In this way, the effect of delivery time is reflected in the objective function through the amount of sales and income. In this model, some distribution channels with different transportation times and costs have been considered between each pair of distribution centers and customers. The transportation costs of the channels are subjected to discounts. The decision variables of the problem are the location of distribution centers, the selection of transportation channels and the assignment of distribution centers to plants. A genetic algorithm and a variable neighborhood search are utilized to solve the problem. The numerical results show that the genetic algorithm generates solutions of higher quality while the other one has a shorter computation time. Finally, a comparison is made between the optimal solutions of this model with a similar case of fixed demand, and it is shown that considering delivery time dependent demand, leads to higher profit.

Keywords: Supply Chain Design, Delivery Time Dependent Demand, Transportation Channel, Discount, Genetic Algorithm, variable Neighborhood Search.